

Ensuring UAS Airworthiness: Deep Learning-Based Acoustic Health Monitoring of Motor Health

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Abstract—As Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are increasingly utilized across various industries and especially in rescue missions, ensuring the reliability and longevity of their powertrain systems is critical for operational safety and efficiency. Traditional fault detection methods often rely on manual inspection or require large, labeled datasets, making them impractical for real-time monitoring in the field. The challenge is further compounded by the high cost and time required to label fault data, making it difficult to implement scalable and effective fault detection tools. This study proposes a semi-supervised approach using a 1D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Autoencoder to address these challenges. The model is trained exclusively on healthy motor acoustics signatures, learning to reconstruct normal acoustic features of the blde motor and demonstrated strong performance in fault detection. The proposed CNN Autoencoder model provides an effective tool enabling early detection of motor failures, enabling predictive maintenance and improving safety. The results highlight the potential of this approach for real-world UAV applications, where acquiring large, labeled datasets is often impractical. The framework developed is proposed to be integrated the In-time Aviation Safety Management System (IASMS) for pre and post flight diagnostics.

Keywords—UAV, predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, convolutional autoencoder, machine learning, acoustic fault diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are increasingly deployed for critical missions, including wildfires extinction [1], [2], and hurricane disaster relief [3] where these vehicles support efforts to help with search-and-rescue operations. It is essential to have the vehicle health at its prime efficiency for effective rescue operation completion. Under the National Academies provided vision for Advanced Air Mobility (AAM) an In-time Aviation Safety Management System (IASMS) is proposed which integrates safety assurance, and is the foundation for In-time System-wide Safety Assurance (ISSA), with traditional risk management process. A Concept of Operations (ConOps) for IASMS is based on requirements to address critical system failures, such as

loss of communication links, loss of battery power, motor failure etc [4]. Loss-of-control risk due to powertrain or flight control system failure is mitigated, which may involve but not limited to the physical operational environment and weather encounters such as wind gusts. Safety risks ensuing from cyber security infractions and malicious threats by people on the ground are also included as part of the IASMS design requirements.

In earlier work [5] Fit2Fly framework was proposed which aims to make future drones safe and reliable. The framework proposed automating traditional aircraft monitoring and inspection activities and integrating them with convergent technologies such as advanced radio spectrum monitoring, cloud-based microservices, etc, specifically designed towards creating financial incentives through safety and efficient flight operation. Each vehicle runs a self-diagnostics test prior to flight; makes Go/No-Go decision to continue with the flight forward and monitoring continues during flight.

One of the critical risks is the Vehicle system failure which can jeopardize the entire missions. The key components as discussed in [4] are batteries and motors. Vehicle health monitoring systems continuously assess performance of on-board operational systems, e.g., battery power and motor performance.

Considering the IASMS Architecture risk mitigation that specifically includes vehicle health and the Fit2Fly pre-flight diagnostics we propose to integrate pre and post diagnostics for motor health as shown in Fig. 1, where in data is collected pre and post flight operations, processed and analyzed through developed algorithms for decision making, a detailed discussion on this schematic follows in the next section. UAV motors, particularly their propellers and bearings, are prone to faults that can degrade performance, compromise safety, and increase maintenance and operational costs. The developed framework facilitates the identification of degradation and failure precursors, thereby preventing the vehicle from any compromised vehicles flying and mitigating the risk of in-flight mishaps during critical missions.

Figure 1: Schematic of proposed framework for pre and post flight procedures to capture acoustic motor health data for fault diagnosis and decision making.

Predictive maintenance has emerged as an effective strategy to address these challenges, leveraging machine learning (ML) techniques to anticipate failures before they occur. In [6] the authors explored the use of ML in predictive maintenance for the automotive industry, highlighting the importance of accurate data representation in ensuring robust failure predictions. Traditional fault diagnosis methods, such as manual inspections, are labor-intensive and susceptible to human error, underscoring the need for automated, data-driven approaches [7].

Acoustic signal analysis has gained prominence as a reliable, non-invasive approach for fault detection, leveraging the distinct sound patterns emitted by mechanical components under wear or failure. For instance, the work in [7] demonstrated that integrating vibro-acoustic data enhances bearing fault diagnosis accuracy. Among various machine learning techniques, Support Vector Machines (SVMs) have been extensively employed for process monitoring and fault classification. Studies such as [8] and [9] discussed the effectiveness of SVMs in handling complex industrial processes, while [10] further demonstrated the applicability of SVM models in sound classification, emphasizing their robustness across diverse acoustic datasets.

More recently, deep learning models, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have demonstrated strong capabilities in extracting fault-related features from audio signals. [11] reviewed bearing failure modes and mechanisms, emphasizing the importance of domain-specific knowledge in feature extraction for fault diagnosis. [12] surveyed the applications of 1D CNNs, detailing their effectiveness in sequential data processing, including acoustic signal analysis. In industrial settings, autoencoders have emerged as powerful tools for unsupervised feature extraction and anomaly detection. [13] demonstrated the utility of one-dimensional convolutional autoencoders for fault diagnosis in multivariate process monitoring, while [14] provided a comprehensive survey on autoencoder design and applications in deep learning.

Recent studies have expanded deep learning-based acoustic models beyond industrial applications into UAV detection and monitoring. [15] demonstrated the effectiveness of deep learning models in acoustic analysis, highlighting their ability to learn intricate patterns in noise-varying environments. [16] applied logistic regression to UAV acoustic detection

in indoor scenarios, while [17] explored functional logistic regression for motor fault classification based on frequency-domain acoustic data. Furthermore, research by [18] on machine learning (ML) applications in acoustics underscored the synergy between advanced algorithms and signal processing techniques, further supporting the feasibility of data-driven UAV fault detection systems.

Hybrid approaches have also gained traction in fault detection research. [19] proposed an intelligent framework combining Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) with autoencoders, leveraging the strengths of multiple ML paradigms for improved detection accuracy. Practical applications of such techniques include noise-vibration-harshness (NVH) analysis in industrial settings, as explored in [20]. [21] contributed to UAV performance improvements through enhanced aerodynamic designs, further facilitating acoustic monitoring applications. Data augmentation techniques have been essential in strengthening ML models for sound classification tasks. [10] compared various augmentation methods, demonstrating their effectiveness in improving model generalization. [22] provided a broader survey on modern augmentation strategies, emphasizing their role in mitigating data scarcity challenges.

Building upon these advancements, this study proposes a semi-supervised approach for UAV motor fault detection using a one-dimensional (1D) Convolutional Autoencoder. Unlike supervised learning methods, which require large labeled datasets, autoencoders enable models to learn the normal operational behavior of UAV motors and identify deviations indicative of faults. By leveraging semi-supervised learning and acoustic signal analysis, this research aims to enhance UAV reliability, reduce dependence on extensive labeled datasets, and improve real-world fault detection capabilities. The findings contribute to the broader field of predictive maintenance by providing scalable and data-efficient solutions for UAV health monitoring.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND USE CASE

The powertrain of UAVs plays a critical role in ensuring operational safety and efficiency. Motors are key subsystems driving essential components such as propellers. During operation, these motors generate complex acoustic signals, which contain valuable information about their health status. By capturing these signals through onboard or ground-based sensors i.e., pre and post flights, it becomes possible to analyze their time-frequency representations, such as Mel-spectrograms, to monitor the motor's health condition in real time.

To integrate monitoring and data capture as part of the ConOps, we propose to capture the acoustics and electrical measurements pre and post flight operations as shown in the schematic of Fig. 1. A set of predefined scenarios are run to capture the motor health data which may last not more than 15-20 secs for each rotor, which can be integrated as part of pre-flight checks performed by the pilot. The algorithm takes in this test run data from the ground sensors, which is then fed to the developed model for fault detection and isolation. This information is further used for taking appropriate decisions autonomously/ human-in-loop, regarding flight operations i.e.

Go / No-Go . Similarly once the vehicle completes its mission and touches back down post Conops procedure is followed to evaluate the motor health and update the model for predictive maintenance decisions as required.

However, the practical deployment of an acoustic-based anomaly detection system in UAVs faces significant challenges. One of the primary obstacles is the inherent scarcity of faulty data. In typical operations, the vast majority of the collected acoustic data reflects normal, healthy motor conditions. Fault occurrences are rare, and when they do happen, they often exhibit only subtle deviations from the norm. These slight changes—whether in amplitude, frequency content, or temporal dynamics—can be easily obscured by environmental noise and operational variability, making them difficult to detect with traditional supervised learning methods that require ample labeled examples of faulty behavior.

This model development study is driven by the need to overcome these challenges. A residual semi-supervised approach is proposed that leverages the abundant healthy motor data to build a robust model of normal acoustic behavior. Thus, the central problem we address is twofold. The aim is to first reliably detect early-stage motor faults based solely on subtle changes in acoustic signatures, even when such deviations are masked by operational noise. Second, develop an anomaly detection framework that is effective despite the limited availability of labeled fault data. By focusing on the residual—i.e., the reconstruction error between the actual signal and its autoencoder-based reconstruction, a sensitive and robust method for identifying anomalies is enabled, ultimately enhancing predictive maintenance capabilities in UAV systems.

A. Dataset Description

To test developed algorithms, we used the "Brushless DC Motor Sound Dataset for Predictive Maintenance" [23]. This dataset was chosen since it used brushless DC motors which are similar to those on our experimental testbed, which is currently used for data collection and model development. The dataset contains 43 ten-second .wav audio samples of motor sounds, recorded at 16 kHz, and is specifically designed for predictive maintenance (PdM) applications using signal processing and machine learning. Future work will focus on integrating our algorithm framework with the testbed.

The recordings were obtained using four A2212 Brushless DC (BLDC) motors connected to an 11.1V LiPo battery, a 30A Electronic Speed Controller (ESC), and an ESP32 microcontroller, which regulated the motor speed via the Blynk platform. A MCJR-005 Capacitor Microphone was used to record the audio signals [23].

The dataset is structured into three distinct categories representing different motor health conditions. The first category consists of healthy motors operating under normal conditions without any detected faults, with motors labeled as M1, M2, and M3. The second category includes recordings of motors experiencing propeller-related issues, specifically affecting motors M1 and M2, which can influence performance and stability. The final category contains recordings from motor M4, which exhibits bearing-related faults, introducing mechanical

noise and vibration irregularities. Each category contains multiple recordings to ensure variability in the dataset, with approximately 20 files representing healthy motor operations, around 10 files capturing propeller fault conditions, and 10 files documenting instances of motors with bearing faults.

B. Data Exploratory Analysis

Recognizing the inherent challenge posed by the limited availability of fault data, we undertook an extensive data exploration process to both understand and enhance the utility of the available recordings.

To increase the effective sample size and better capture the temporal characteristics of the motor sounds, each 10-second recording was segmented into three shorter chunks of approximately 3.33 seconds. This segmentation strategy resulted in roughly 60 samples for healthy motor conditions and about 30 samples for each fault category (propeller and bearing faults). Although splitting the recordings into smaller segments raised concerns about potentially losing longer-term temporal variations, subsequent analyses confirmed that the essential characteristics of the motor acoustics were preserved.

Following segmentation, a comprehensive feature engineering process was undertaken to transform the raw audio signals into representations amenable to machine learning. Both time-domain and frequency-domain features were extracted to ensure a thorough characterization of the motor sounds. In the time domain, the Root Mean Square (RMS) energy was computed to reflect the average power of the signal over time—a measure that can indicate increased mechanical stress when RMS values are high. These are key indicators to observe degradation in the motor health under high stress operations. In addition, the zero-crossing rate (ZCR) was calculated to assess the signal's noisiness and periodicity, which can help differentiate between normal and faulty motor states. For frequency-domain analysis, Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) were extracted, as they capture perceptually relevant acoustic features. Spectrograms and Mel-spectrograms were generated to visualize the evolution of frequency components over time, providing deeper insight into the acoustic patterns associated with different motor health states.

A total of 22 features were extracted from the audio signals to capture both time-domain and frequency-domain characteristics of motor behavior. To enhance efficiency and reduce redundancy, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to transform the data into a lower-dimensional space while preserving the most informative components. Given the potential correlation among extracted features, PCA helped in identifying key discriminative patterns by maximizing variance while minimizing dimensionality.

Figure 2 illustrates the cumulative explained variance as a function of the number of principal components. The curve shows that a small subset of components accounts for most of the variance, demonstrating that the feature space can be effectively reduced without significant information loss.

Further analysis of one of the most relevant features revealed distinct amplitude trends within specific frequency

TABLE I. Frequency Buckets for Different Motor Conditions

Category	0–1000 Hz	1000–2000 Hz	2000–3000 Hz	3000–4000 Hz	4000–5000 Hz	5000–6000 Hz
Healthy	0.00011	0.00010	9.9e-05	9.8e-05	0.00010	0.000101
Bearing	7.7e-05	6.8e-05	8.7e-05	8.3e-05	8.6e-05	8.0e-05
Propeller	0.00076	0.00094	0.00087	0.00093	0.00077	0.00093

Figure 2: Cumulative Explained Variance by Number of Principal Components. The curve shows that most of the variance is captured within the first few principal components, justifying dimensionality reduction.

buckets across different motor conditions. As shown in Table I, healthy motors, motors with bearing faults, and motors with propeller faults exhibit distinct frequency responses, confirming the discriminative power of the extracted features.

These findings validate that both time-domain and frequency-domain features provide crucial insights into motor condition monitoring. The distinct amplitude variations in specific frequency bands indicate that the extracted features can effectively differentiate between healthy and faulty motors, reinforcing their suitability for training predictive models for fault detection.

Furthermore, we generated spectrograms and Mel-spectrograms (as seen in Figure 3) to visualize the evolution of the frequency spectrum over time; these representations offer a three-dimensional view of the signal, with frequency, time, and amplitude depicted simultaneously. Mel-spectrograms, in particular, transform the frequency scale to align more closely with human auditory perception. To complement these features, wavelet coefficients were also extracted, enabling a multiscale analysis that highlights both high-frequency and low-frequency changes, which are useful for detecting transient anomalies indicative of early-stage faults.

Spectrograms played a crucial role in visualizing the differences between healthy and faulty motor states. A spectrogram converts an audio signal into a 2D image, mapping time and frequency to a visual format that reveals how sound properties change over time. This type of analysis is particularly useful in applications involving machinery, as it allows for the

Figure 3: Mel-spectrograms for different motor conditions: (a) Healthy motor, (b) Motor with propeller fault, (c) Motor with bearing fault. The distinct frequency variations highlight fault-specific characteristics.

identification of periodic anomalies and transient noise that could indicate mechanical issues. In this analysis, representative spectrograms were selected from each class (healthy, propeller fault, and bearing fault) for comparison. Healthy motors showed consistent, stable distributions across time, with few irregularities. Bearing faults exhibited disruptions in specific frequency ranges, often in the mid-to-high frequency spectrum. These disruptions were represented by periodic spikes or changes in amplitude. Propeller faults presented more irregular and dispersed frequency patterns, with certain vertical bands of inconsistent amplitudes in intervals of time.

In addition a PCA analysis was conducted on spectrogram images and the results confirmed clear separability between the motor health conditions. This reinforced the potential of spectrograms as rich data sources for training predictive models. By maintaining both the time and frequency dimensions, spectrograms provide an ideal balance between temporal resolution and frequency content, supporting models in learning to distinguish different motor states effectively.

The exploratory data analysis revealed significant variations in both feature-engineered data and spectrogram representations among healthy, propeller fault, and bearing fault motor states. Spectrograms provided a complementary perspective, illustrating time-frequency relationships in a visual format. Healthy motors exhibited stable and consistent patterns, while propeller and bearing faults introduced visible disruptions and irregularities in specific frequency ranges. These observations underscore the ability of spectrograms to encapsulate complex temporal and spectral changes associated with mechanical faults. The PCA analysis further confirmed that both feature-engineered data and spectrogram representations captured sufficient information to distinguish between motor states. The separability observed in the PCA plots demonstrates the potential of these data representations to support predictive

modeling tasks.

To further evaluate the effectiveness of use of spectrograms on this segmented data, two standard classification models were implemented: Logistic Regression for binary classification (healthy vs. faulty) and Support Vector Machine for multi-class classification (healthy, propeller fault, and bearing fault). Both supervised models were trained on an 80-20 split of the labeled dataset to maintain balanced representation across motor conditions. The Logistic Regression model achieved perfect classification, with precision, recall, and F1-scores of 1.0 across all classes, confirming that all classifications made on the test set were correct, with no false positives and false negatives. Similarly, the SVM classifier demonstrated flawless separation between motor conditions, further reinforcing the robustness of the extracted features. This success highlights the clear separability of motor conditions based on spectrogram features, validating the dataset's quality and establishing a solid basis for further exploration into more sophisticated learning techniques, including semi-supervised approaches.

In summary, the exploratory data analysis provided key insights into the structure and quality of the dataset, guiding the subsequent machine learning model development.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for motor fault detection is structured around a semi-supervised learning framework utilizing a 1D CNN Autoencoder to classify the health conditions of brushless DC (BLDC) motors based on their acoustic signatures. This approach prioritizes the semi-supervised model due to its practical advantages in real-world applications, particularly its ability to function effectively without requiring extensive labeled datasets. To provide a reference for evaluating performance, traditional supervised learning models were also implemented, serving as benchmark methods. These baseline models, trained on labeled data, offer insight into the discriminative power of the extracted acoustic features and establish an upper bound on classification performance under ideal conditions. The study employs spectrogram transformations of audio signals as input representations, leveraging their ability to preserve temporal and spectral characteristics crucial for fault detection. The primary objective is to distinguish between healthy motors and those exhibiting propeller or bearing faults, demonstrating the efficacy of the semi-supervised framework in detecting anomalies while mitigating the dependency on labeled fault data.

A. Data Preprocessing and Augmentation

Given the limited number of fault recordings and the predominance of healthy data, we augmented the effective sample size by segmenting each 10-second audio clip into three 3.33-second chunks. This strategy increased the number of samples for healthy conditions and provided a sufficient, though imbalanced, representation of fault conditions (e.g., propeller and bearing faults). The data pre-processing steps in this methodology involve several key stages, which were necessary to convert the raw audio data into a format suitable for feeding into the CNN Autoencoder.

Audio Data Segmentation and Augmentation : The raw audio files from healthy and faulty BLDC motors were segmented into smaller chunks of approximately 3.33 seconds each. This segmentation ensured a consistent input size for training and testing.

To overcome the small size of the healthy dataset, synthetic data augmentation techniques were applied. These included time-stretching, pitch-shifting, and adding noise to the original audio recordings. As a result, the healthy dataset was expanded to approximately 1000 samples to provide the network with enough examples of normal motor behavior.

To confirm that this significant data augmentation did not compromise the quality or representativeness of the original data, a test was performed to assess whether the augmented dataset retained the key information from the smaller original dataset. A logistic regression model was trained on a mixed dataset that included both the augmented healthy data and original healthy data combined with balanced, augmented and original unhealthy data. A confusion matrix summarizing classification accuracy on augmented data is presented in Figure 5.

Spectrogram Conversion and Normalization : Following segmentation and augmentation, the raw audio signals were transformed into Mel-spectrograms, which serve as a time-frequency representation of motor sounds. Each spectrogram was computed using 128 Mel frequency bands to capture a broad range of acoustic features, while 44 time frames were used to preserve the temporal evolution of the signal. These spectrograms provided the fundamental input for subsequent feature extraction and model training.

To ensure consistency across the dataset and enhance computational efficiency, all spectrogram values were normalized using MinMax scaling, mapping them to the range [0,1]. This transformation, defined by the equation:

$$X' = \frac{X - X_{\min}}{X_{\max} - X_{\min}} \quad (1)$$

ensures that all features contribute proportionally to the learning process, preventing any single feature from dominating due to scale differences.

For model development, the dataset was divided into three subsets: 60% for training, consisting exclusively of healthy motor data to support semi-supervised learning, 20% for validation to monitor performance and optimize hyperparameters, and 20% for testing, containing both healthy and faulty motor signals.

Figure 3 illustrates examples of Mel-spectrograms for different motor conditions, highlighting distinct spectral patterns corresponding to healthy and faulty states. Healthy motors exhibit stable and consistent distributions over time, with minimal irregularities. In contrast, motors with bearing faults display disruptions in specific frequency ranges, particularly in the mid-to-high frequency spectrum, often characterized by periodic spikes and amplitude fluctuations. Meanwhile, propeller faults generate more irregular and dispersed frequency patterns, with inconsistent amplitude variations appearing intermittently across different time intervals.

Figure 4: Overview of the proposed UAV motor fault detection framework. The process begins with **Data Pre-Processing**, where raw acoustic signals undergo augmentation techniques such as adding noise, pitch shifting, and time stretching. Next, a **1D CNN Autoencoder** is employed to learn the normal acoustic patterns of healthy motors. During the **Training** phase, the model is trained exclusively on healthy data, using Mel-spectrograms as input. Finally, in the **Classification** stage, anomalies are identified based on the reconstruction error, with the anomaly score determining whether a motor is classified as healthy or faulty.

Figure 5: Confusion matrix demonstrating classification accuracy on augmented data.

These spectrogram-based representations serve as the foundation for training machine learning models, enabling them to differentiate between normal and faulty states by capturing the unique spectral characteristics associated with each fault type.

B. Residual-based 1D CNN Autoencoder

To detect anomalies in UAV motor acoustic signals, a 1D Convolutional Autoencoder (CAE) was selected, leveraging its ability to learn normal motor behavior and flag deviations indicative of potential faults. The CAE follows a self-

supervised learning paradigm, where it is trained exclusively on healthy motor data. When exposed to anomalous signals, the model struggles to reconstruct them accurately, resulting in increased reconstruction errors, which serve as the basis for fault detection.

Although Mel-spectrograms are two-dimensional representations, their key fault-related characteristics lie in the temporal evolution of frequency components. A 1D CNN is better suited for capturing these variations along the time axis, making it more efficient and interpretable for detecting subtle acoustic anomalies. Compared to a 2D CNN, a 1D CNN requires fewer computational resources, reducing training time and complexity, while still preserving critical fault-related features. Additionally, its simpler architecture mitigates the risk of overfitting, ensuring a robust and generalizable model.

The CAE consists of an encoder that compresses spectrogram input into a lower-dimensional representation and a decoder that reconstructs the spectrogram from this latent space. The encoder is composed of three 1D convolutional layers, progressively reducing the spectrogram's temporal dimension while extracting hierarchical features. The first layer applies 128 filters with a kernel size of 3, followed by a 64-filter layer, and a 32-filter layer, all using ReLU activation. The final layer forms a bottleneck representation, capturing the most salient features of the motor sound.

The decoder mirrors the encoder's structure, reconstructing the input using three transposed convolutional layers. The first transposed layer applies 32 filters, followed by 64 filters in the second layer, and 128 filters in the third. The output layer employs a sigmoid activation function, ensuring the reconstructed spectrogram maintains values within a normalized range. The complete model architecture is depicted in Figure

6, illustrating how the encoder compresses input data and the decoder reconstructs it, enabling anomaly detection through reconstruction errors.

Figure 6: 1D CNN Autoencoder architecture for anomaly detection. The encoder extracts key temporal features, while the decoder reconstructs the input, allowing for fault detection based on reconstruction errors.

C. Anomaly Detection via Reconstruction Residuals

Once the autoencoder is trained, new acoustic inputs are processed through the network, and their reconstruction errors are computed. We define the reconstruction error—the residual—as the mean squared difference between the original and reconstructed spectrograms. A threshold is established based on the 95th percentile of reconstruction errors from the training (healthy) data. Signals with reconstruction errors exceeding this threshold are flagged as anomalous, indicating potential motor faults.

Once trained, the autoencoder was used to evaluate test samples. Anomalies were detected based on the reconstruction error, defined as the mean squared difference between the original and reconstructed spectrogram:

$$E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \hat{X}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

To classify samples as normal or faulty, a threshold was set based on the 95th percentile of reconstruction errors from the training data. The anomaly score S for each test sample was computed as:

$$S = \frac{E}{E_{95}} \quad (3)$$

where E_{95} represents the 95th percentile of training set errors. A sample was classified as faulty if $S > 1$, otherwise it was classified as normal:

$$\text{Label} = \begin{cases} 0, & S \leq 1 \quad (\text{Healthy}) \\ 1, & S > 1 \quad (\text{Unhealthy}) \end{cases}$$

D. Training and Evaluation

Next, the network’s hyperparameters—including the number of convolutional layers, filter sizes, and learning rate—were fine-tuned using a grid search combined with cross-validation on the healthy data. This rigorous tuning ensured that the model architecture was optimally configured to capture the inherent temporal and spectral features of the motor acoustics.

The model was trained to minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the original spectrogram input and its reconstructed version:

$$\mathcal{L}_{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \hat{X}_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

where X_i is the original spectrogram window, and \hat{X}_i is the reconstructed output. The Adam optimizer was used for training with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 10.

To monitor the training process and guard against overfitting, a separate validation set was employed. The training was continuously evaluated on this set, and early stopping was implemented based on the validation loss, thereby halting training once performance improvements plateaued.

To establish a performance benchmark and validate the discriminative power of our engineered features, we first implemented traditional supervised classification models—namely, Logistic Regression (LR) and Support Vector Machines (SVM). These base supervised models were trained on the segmented and feature-transformed data, using an 80/20 training-test split to ensure balanced representation across classes.

Following training, the performance of the semi-supervised 1D CNN Autoencoder was rigorously compared against baseline models, including Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machines. Evaluation metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score were computed, and the results were further analyzed using confusion matrices and precision-recall curves. This comparative evaluation provided clear insights into the effectiveness of our residual-based detection approach, demonstrating its capability to identify anomalies even in the absence of extensive labeled fault data.

IV. RESULTS

The effectiveness of the proposed 1D CNN Autoencoder for UAV motor fault detection is assessed through key performance metrics, including precision, recall, and confusion matrix analysis. The model employs the anomaly score as the primary anomaly indicator, where reconstruction errors above a set threshold signal potential faults.

The confusion matrix, illustrated in Figure 7, visualizes the classification outcomes at a 95% detection threshold, showing

TABLE II. Comparison of Logistic Regression (Supervised) and 1D CNN Autoencoder (Semi-Supervised) for Healthy-Unhealthy Classification

Model	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1-Score	Specificity	MCC	AUC-ROC	False Positive (%)	False Negative (%)
Logistic Regression	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00%	0.00%
1D CNN Autoencoder	0.871	0.857	0.957	0.864	0.962	0.852	0.95	3.77%	14.29%

the distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified samples. The model correctly identified 204 healthy and 54 unhealthy samples, demonstrating high accuracy in both categories. However, 8 healthy samples were misclassified as unhealthy (false positives), and 9 unhealthy samples were incorrectly classified as healthy (false negatives). The relatively low false negative rate suggests that the model effectively captures most faults, although further optimization and additional training data could improve sensitivity to subtle fault conditions.

Figure 7: Confusion Matrix at 95% Threshold, illustrating classification performance for healthy and unhealthy UAV motors.

The precision-recall curve, shown in Figure 8, evaluates the trade-off between precision (the proportion of correctly identified faults) and recall (the proportion of actual faults detected). At the 95% threshold, the model achieved a precision of 0.87 and a recall of 0.86, indicating a well-balanced detection performance. The curve demonstrates that the model maintains high precision across varying recall levels, though precision begins to decrease at higher recall values. This suggests that increasing sensitivity for fault detection may lead to a higher false alarm rate.

The results demonstrate the strength of the 1D CNN Autoencoder in detecting anomalies and faults in UAV motor acoustic signals, even with limited fault data. The high precision and recall at the 95% threshold reflect the model's robustness in distinguishing between healthy and faulty motor conditions. The ability to detect subtle acoustic anomalies through reconstruction residuals underscores the effectiveness of the semi-supervised learning framework. The model can still identify fault signatures from signals it has not explicitly seen during training. The confusion matrix further confirmed

Figure 8: Precision-Recall Curve at 95% Threshold, highlighting the model's trade-off between fault detection accuracy and false positive rate.

the model's performance, indicating that it correctly classified the majority of healthy and faulty motors, although there was room for improvement in reducing false positives and improving sensitivity to subtle fault conditions. The precision-recall curve highlighted the trade-off between precision and recall, suggesting that further optimization could lead to better recall without increasing false positives. These results underscore the potential of the 1D CNN Autoencoder for UAV motor fault detection, demonstrating its ability to effectively identify faults with limited labeled data, although future work will focus on improving the sensitivity and reducing false alarms to ensure more accurate detection across a wider range of motor operational conditions.

The results underscore a significant trade-off between the semi-supervised 1D CNN Autoencoder and the baseline supervised models, such as Logistic Regression as presented in Table II. Although the supervised models exhibit marginally superior performance in classification accuracy, their dependence on labeled fault data and balanced training sets renders them less practical for real-world applications. In practice, obtaining large volumes of labeled fault data is often labor-intensive, time-consuming, and resource-intensive. These supervised models necessitate a well-balanced dataset that includes a sufficient number of both healthy and faulty motor instances, which is not always feasible in majority of operational contexts. In contrast, the semi-supervised 1D CNN Autoencoder, while demonstrating slightly reduced accuracy, offers a more pragmatic and scalable solution by mitigating the need for extensive labeled fault data and balanced datasets. By utilizing primarily healthy motor data

to learn normal motor behavior, the semi-supervised model is capable of effectively identifying anomalies in unseen data, thus making it better suited for real-world scenarios where fault data is limited or imbalanced. This trade-off—slightly lower performance in exchange for enhanced practicality and data efficiency—demonstrates the advantages of the semi-supervised approach, particularly in applications where the acquisition and labeling of extensive fault data is not a feasible option.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the feasibility of detecting and classifying faults in UAV motors using acoustic signals and advanced machine learning techniques. The research demonstrated that acoustic signals, particularly those converted into Mel-spectrograms, contain rich information that can be leveraged for effective fault detection. Both supervised and semi-supervised models were tested to evaluate their performance in identifying anomalies and classifying motor conditions. The results from the supervised models, specifically logistic regression and SVM classifiers, showed perfect classification accuracy, with all instances correctly identified as healthy or faulty. These results were achieved due to the highly informative nature of the acoustic features used for training, which facilitated robust differentiation between motor conditions. The inclusion of augmented data in the training phase further confirmed that such an approach could maintain high classification performance without losing the essential characteristics of the original dataset. In the semi-supervised phase, the CNN Autoencoder model was successfully trained using only healthy data and was capable of detecting anomalies across both healthy and faulty samples. The autoencoder's performance emphasized the utility of unsupervised anomaly detection methods in applications where labeled data may be limited, making it a valuable tool for predictive maintenance.

Overall, the findings from this research highlight the potential for applying machine learning models to UAV motor health monitoring. These approaches can enhance safety by allowing early detection of faults before they lead to failures, thereby contributing to the reliability and longevity of UAV systems. Future work could involve testing these models on larger, more diverse datasets and exploring their applicability in real-world scenarios. Additionally, extending the models to perform detailed classifications, such as identifying specific fault types (e.g., propeller versus bearing failures), as well as predicting the remaining useful life (RUL) of the motors, would further improve their utility in predictive maintenance applications.

As future work, we plan to integrate the developed diagnostic framework into the IASMS ConOps for both pre- and post-flight operations. This integration will allow for estimating the powertrain health and can help the operators take decisions for operating the mission flights. Furthermore, we will develop additional experiments to learn and refine the models by integrating additional motor electrical parameters data along with the current acoustics data with the goal of generalizing them for use with a wider range of powertrain systems.

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